

A new subspecies of *Psilotarsus brachypterus* (Gebler, 1830) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from South-East Kazakhstan

M.L. Danilevsky

A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution, Russian Academy of Sciences

Leninsky prospect, 33, Moscow 119071 Russia

e-mail: danilevsky@cerambycidae.net

ORCID 0000-0001-8079-3343

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Prioninae, Prionini, taxonomy, new subspecies, Kazakhstan.

Abstract. *Psilotarsus brachypterus alakolensis* **ssp. nov.** is described from South-East Kazakhstan (Almaty reg., 30 km N of Zhanama, 46°27'N, 80°39'E, 18.6.2024). 133 males were collected at light by 3 persons: K. Hodek, M. Holomčík, F. Klabusay. The new subspecies is very close to the nominative one but differs by several small features. The distinguishing characters are discussed and illustrated.

Introduction

Psilotarsus brachypterus (Gebler, 1830) is accepted now with 5 subspecies distributed from East to West Kazakhstan, in Central Asia (Uzbekistan), China (Xinjiang) and in the Asian parts of Orenburg Region (West Siberia, Russia).

The original description was based on 2 females: “alterum ad fl. Irtysh, alterum in deserto Kirghisico”. Types are not known, but 5 specimens (4 males and 1 female) from Irtysh valley (Slavyanka environs) are available in author’s collection.

The nominative subspecies *P. b. brachypterus* (Gebler, 1830) is distributed from Russian South-West Siberia (south of Orenburg Region) through East Kazakhstan to the south of East Kazakhstan Region (Zaisan Depression). The taxon is also known from China (Xinjiang). A population from near Zaisan Lake only is now available for study by the author. Other populations could represent another subspecies not described yet.

P. b. hemipterus (Motschulsky, 1845) - according to Danilevsky (2000), the taxon was described from Tersakan river valley, not far from the source of Turgai river (Arkalyk env.).

M.L. Danilevsky

It is distributed in north-west, north and partly central Kazakhstan: from Orenburg district of Russia southwards to Sary-Su river and low Syr-Darja river in Kazakhstan and further south to Samarkand region in Uzbekistan; and from Ural-river valley, through Aktiube region, south of Kustanai region (Arkalyk environs) to about Akmola and Karaganda regions.

P. b. aralensis Danilevsky, 2000 was described from Ustiurt plateau - West Kazakhstan and West Karakalpakia in West Uzbekistan, between Caspian and Aral seas.

P. b. pubiventris (Semenov, 1900) was described from near “Vernyj” (now Almaty in Kazakhstan). It is distributed in Kazakhstan along planes and foothills from Chu-Ili mountains in the West to about Chilik and Dzungarsky Alatau eastwards; and from Balkhash lake in the North to about north slope of Zailiysky Alatau.

P. b. alpherakii (Semenov, 1900) was described from China (Yining environs). It is distributed in China Dzhungarie between Kuldzha (now Yining) and Kazakhstan border, so most probably the taxon occurs also in Kazakhstan in the environs of Dzsharkent.

The occurrence of the species in Alakol Lake depression was known from long ago. Danilevsky (2000: 50) recorded the dry debris from the area, which were preliminary identified as *P. b. pubiventris*. Recently a huge series of males was collected there by Czech entomologists. New material is described below as a new subspecies.

Results

Psilotarsus brachypterus alakolensis ssp. nov.

Figs 1-2, 4, 6, 8, 10

Description. Body (including antennae, elytra and legs) dark-brown (Figs 1-2), nearly black; head relatively small; eyes big, the distance between dorsal eye lobes a little less than width of 1st antennal joint; last joint of maxillary palpi considerably attenuated; antennae long, reaching last elytral 7th, strongly serrated, slightly lightened apically; middle antennal joints flat, triangular, acute (Fig. 6); 1st antennal joint very short, nearly globose (Fig. 6); prothorax (Fig. 8) strongly

M.L. Danilevsky

transverse, about 1,9 times wider than long, with very fine scattered short pubescence, often glabrous at middle, often densely pubescent laterally; lateral thoracic spines short, posterior lateral thoracic spines often totally obliterated; pronotal punctation moderately rough; elytra moderately narrowed posteriorly, about 1.6 times longer than basal width, rounded apically or with hardly distinct sutural angle; tarsal pads strongly reduced, sometimes indistinct; metathorax with dense, long pubescence, which is shorter and sparser along episternum; abdomen strongly shining, with scattered short pubescence; last abdominal tergite rounded, with very small emargination; last abdominal sternite shallowly emarginated; male genitals - see Fig. 10; body length: 19-31.5 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *P. b. alakolensis* **ssp. nov.** is close to the nominative subspecies (Fig. 3, 7, 9), but *P. b. brachypterus* (Gebler, 1830), is distributed eastwards and differs by many characters: eyes smaller, the distance between dorsal eye lobes longer than width of 1st antennal joint; antennae reddish; 1st antennal joint elongated, distinctly longer than wide (Figs. 6-7); prothorax (Figs. 8-9) less wide, with about 1.8 times wider than long; posterior pronotal angles small, but distinct; pronotal punctations rougher; tarsal pads wider; metathorax pubescence shorter and sparser, episterna pubescence much sparser.

Type material. Holotype (Fig. 1), male, Kazakhstan, Almaty region, 30 km N of Zhanama, 46°27'56.26"S, 80°39'31.77"W, 18.6.2024, K. Hodek leg. (author's collection); paratypes: 5 males with the same label (author's collection); 53 males, with the same label (collection of K. Hodek, Brno - Štýřice); 35 males, same data, M. Holomčik leg. (collection of M. Holomčik, Lusatia); 45 males, same data, F. Klabusay leg. (collection of F. Klabusay, Brno).

Material used for comparison. 2 males (32 mm & 23 mm), E Kazakhstan, north bank of Zaisan Lake near Slavianka, 420 m, 24.6.1997, V. Lukhtanov leg. (author's collection); 1 male, E Kazakhstan, Monrak Ridge, Priozernyi env., 900 m, 20.6.1997, V. Lukhtanov leg. (author's collection); 1 male, E Kazakhstan, Saur Ridge, Kenderlik river, 900 m, 5.7.1997, V. Lukhtanov leg. (author's collection).

Fig. 1. Holotype of *Psilotarsus brachypterus alakolensis* **ssp. nov.**

Fig. 2. Paratype of *P. b. alakolensis* **ssp. nov.** Photo by K. Hodek.

Fig. 3. Male of *P. b. brachypterus* (Gebler, 1830), Kazakhstan, northern shore of Zaisan Lake, Slavianka, 24.6.1997, V. Lukhtanov leg.

Fig. 4. *P. b. alakolensis* **ssp. nov.** in nature. Photo by K. Hodek.

Fig. 5. Landscape of the type locality of *P. b. alakolensis* **ssp. nov.** Photo by K. Hodek.

Figs. 6-7. Head and basal antennal joints: 6 - *P. b. alakolensis* ssp. nov.; 7 - *P. b. brachypterus*.

Figs. 8-9. Pronotum: 8 - *P. b. alakolensis* ssp. nov.; 9 - *P. b. brachypterus*.

Fig. 10. Median lobes of aedeagus and parameres of *P. b. alakolensis* ssp. nov. Photo by K. Hodek.

M.L. Danilevsky

Bionomy. K. Hodek wrote to me: “All specimens were caught on a light trap only, roughly from dusk at 8:15 p.m. (23°C) to 11:00 p.m. (20°C), when it cooled down. Only males were caught, all and only when they arrived at the light trap. At the same time, a search of the steppe (Fig. 5) in the wider area was also carried out with a flashlight, no (!) specimen was found outside the light trap - neither males nor females. It was probably the beginning of swarming, all specimens found are in excellent condition and without damage.”

Etymology. The new taxon is named after the region where it is found.

Acknowledgements. I am very grateful to my Czech colleagues K. Hodek (Brno - Štýřice, Czech Republic), M. Holomčik (Lusatia, Czech Republic) & F. Klabusay (Brno, Czech Republic) for supplying me with specimens for study.

REFERENCES

- Danilevsky M.L. 2000. Review of genus *Psilotarsus* Motschulsky, 1860, stat. rest. (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Prioninae). - Les Cahiers Magellanes. 3: 1-34.
- Gebler F.A. von. 1830. Bemerkungen über die Insecten Sibiriens, vorzüglich des Altai. (Part III). Pp. 1-228. - In: C.F. Ledebour (ed.): Reise durch das Altai-Gebirge und die soongorische Kirgisen-Steppe. Auf Kosten der Kaiserlichen Universität Dorpat unternommen im Jahre 1826 in Begleitung der Herren D. Carl Anton Meyer und D. Alexander von Bunge R. K. Collegien-Assessors. Zweiter Theil. Berlin: G. Reimer, iv + 522 + [2] pp.
- Motschulsky V. de 1845. Remarques sur la collection de coléoptères russes de M. [Motschoulsky]. Article I.- Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou, 18 (1): 1-127, pls 5-7. [Corrections in 18 (2) Additum, post p. 549 (unnumbered)].

Received: 30.12.2024

Accepted: 10.03.2025